

MONOHYDROXO-TRICHLORO-ANTIMONITE COMPLEX

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The high solubility of antimony trichloride in water is due to the formation of monoquo-trichloro antimony complex $[SbCl_3(H_2O)]$, which behaves as a monobasic acid. In the saturated aqueous solution the reaction could not proceed to a very great extent due to the want of sufficient number of water molecules. A dioxan salt containing one molecule of dioxan, one of water and three chlorine atoms per atom of antimony has been prepared and analysed, and the constitution (I) assigned to it.

The high solubility of antimony chloride (72 g. mols. of $SbCl_3$ at 20° in 100 g. mol. of water) according to Sidgwick ("The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", 1950, p. 793) is due to the complex formation. The addition of alkali chloride, preventing precipitation and at the same time reducing the acidity, supports the complex formation (cf. Sidgwick, *loc.cit.*). The nature of the complex is, however, not discussed. This work was undertaken to study the complexes present in saturated aqueous solution of antimony trichloride.

The high solubility of antimony chloride in water is assumed to be due to the formation of monoquo-trichloro-antimony complex $[SbCl_3(H_2O)]$. Some aquo-complexes have been reported to dissociate into hydrogen ion and hydroxo-complex (Emeleus and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", 1938, p. 158; Pani *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 537, 572). It is assumed here that the above aquo-trichloro-antimony complex reacts as :

As free proton cannot exist in the solution, water molecule is essential for the above reaction. Since the amount of free water in the saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride is small, the above reaction will take place to a very small extent, and major portion of antimony in the solution will be present as aquo-trichloro-complex. The solution is, however, acidic to litmus and methyl orange. It is strange to note that a red colour is developed when phenolphthalein is added to a saturated solution of antimony trichloride. This phenomenon might be due to some other reasons. The acidity of the solution might also be due to hydrolysis of antimony trichloride which appears to be less probable due to the following reasons. Solid antimony oxide or oxychloride does not separate out from the saturated solutions. Addition of solid sodium hydroxide to a saturated solution of antimony chloride does not produce any change (sodium hydroxide most probably goes into solution very slowly but no precipitate is obtained). Solid silver nitrate, when added to the solution, remains unchanged. These observations clearly indicate the absence of hydrolysis; the existence of the aquo-trichloro and hydroxo-trichloro complexes appears to be more probable.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Dioxan Compound.—A saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride (72 g. mol./100 g. mol.) was treated with an excess of dioxan, evolving large amount of heat. When the solution had cooled a white crystalline substance separated out. It was filtered, washed with dioxan, followed by ether, and dried over sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator.

The compound is a white crystalline solid, stable in dry air. It melts at 123° , but decomposes above the melting point. It is hydrolysed by water. It is slightly soluble in ether and completely so in concentrated sulphuric acid. When a solution in sulphuric acid is heated, it turns black due to charring, and on further heating carbon dioxide is liberated.

A known amount of the substance was dissolved in HCl and the antimony content was determined by standard potassium bromate solution. A known amount of the substance was boiled with a known excess of standard NaOH solution and the excess alkali back-titrated using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The compound was completely decomposed by NaOH producing antimony oxide and sodium chloride. The chlorine content was calculated from the alkali required to decompose the substance (Lea and Wood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 139).

To confirm the results obtained above, a known amount of the substance was boiled with excess of alkali, the resulting mixture was acidified with dilute nitric acid and then neutralised with calcium carbonate. It was filtered and the residue (antimony oxide and calcium carbonate) was washed with water till free of chloride. The chloride in the filtrate was estimated by standard silver nitrate solution using potassium chromate as the indicator. Carbon and hydrogen were also estimated by combustion. The results indicate (Table below) that the substance contains one dioxan molecule, three chlorine atoms and one water molecule per atom of antimony. The empirical formula may be written as $D. SbCl_3. H_2O$ where D represents a molecule of dioxan.

	Found.	Calc. for the formula $D, SbCl_3. H_2O$
Sb	36.14% 35.93	36.4%
Cl	31.79 31.80	31.85
C	13.89	14.4
H	3.01	2.99

The dioxan and water molecule present in the compound could not be removed in vacuum over H_2SO_4 , indicating that they are very firmly bound. Dioxan having a great proton affinity very likely extracts the proton from the water molecule of the aquo-trichloro-antimony complex thus:

and the substance behaves as a salt. This assumption is supported by the firmly bound water and dioxan molecule in the compound and the large amount of heat evolved due to the formation of the compound.

This view is also supported by the observation that the saturated solution of antimony chloride in water reacts with calcium carbonate evolving carbon dioxide; but after addition of excess of dioxan to the solution it fails to react with calcium carbonate.

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